

Synthesis of Some New Benzimidazoles as Antiamoebic Agents

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Manuscript received 31 July 1981, revised 5 December 1981, accepted 7 June 1982

Fourteen new substituted 1'-acetyl [3N-aminomethyl substituted quinazolono]-2'-alkyl substituted phthalamido benzimidazoles have been synthesised and their effect on the axenic culture of *Entamoeba histolytica* have been studied *in vitro* at 125 µg/ml. Some of them have shown significant antiamoebic activity.

THE discovery and success of metronidazole (2-methyl-5-nitro-1-ethanol imidazole) as a potent amoebicidal agent stimulated research in imidazole chemistry. A number of compounds of this category have been synthesised and tested for various therapeutic effects¹⁻⁸. Some nitro imidazoles⁴⁻⁷ have been shown to possess marked amoebicidal and trichomonocidal activity. A lot of work has also been done with the benzimidazole moiety as benzimidazoles have shown significant antibacterial, antiviral and antifungal activity^{8,9}. This prompted us to synthesise some substituted benzimidazoles and screen them for amoebicidal activity.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds synthesised were determined in open capillary tubes. Infrared spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. NMR spectra were taken on Perkin-Elmer model R32 at a frequency of 90 MHz. TLC was carried out by using silica-gel coated glass plates of 2 mm thickness, using benzene-methanol (10 : 1) as the solvent.

Infrared spectra : The infrared spectra of the compounds in Tables 1, 2 and 3 show sharp peaks at 3000-3400 cm⁻¹ (-NH), 1700 cm⁻¹ (-C-NH)

and 1500 cm⁻¹ (-NO₂).

NMR spectra (DMSO-d₆) : These benzimidazoles gave a singlet at δ 2.26 for N-CH₃-N, singlet at δ 4.28 for N-CH₂-C and multiplet between

δ 6.24-δ 8.38 for the aromatic protons.

The identity of the compounds was further confirmed by their melting points and elemental analysis, while the purity was ascertained by thin layer chromatography.

2-Alkyl substituted benzimidazoles : These were prepared by the method of Cescon and Day¹⁰.

3-Nitro phthalic anhydride : This was synthesised by the method given in Vogel¹¹.

Substituted 3-N-aminomethyl 4(3H)quinazolones : The method of Mukerji and Nautiyal¹² was followed for the synthesis of these quinazolones.

2-[Phthalamido-alkyl]-benzimidazoles (a) : 2-Alkyl substituted benzimidazole (0.01 mole), 3-nitro phthalic anhydride (0.01 mole) and dry pyridine (7 ml) were refluxed together for 5-6 hr on a sand bath. The reaction mixture, after cooling, was poured into ice-cold water containing a few drops of conc. HCl. The precipitate was filtered, washed with cold water, dried and crystallised from ethanol.

Four new 2-[phthalamido-alkyl]-benzimidazoles were thus synthesised (Table 1).

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	R	R ₂	m.p. °C	Molecular formula
1.	CH ₃	H	242	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂
2.	CH ₂ CH ₃	H	264(d)	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂
3.	CH ₃	3-NO ₂	>275	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₄
4.	CH ₂ CH ₃	3-NO ₂	242	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₄

Yield ranged between 55-60 %.

%N within ± 0.3% of the theoretical values.

3-[N-(Chloroacetyl)-aminomethyl]4(3H)quinazolones (b) : To substituted 3-N-aminomethyl 4(3H)quinazolone (0.01 mole)¹³, chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mole) was added and the mixture refluxed for 2-2½ hr in presence of dry benzene (12 ml). The flask was cooled, excess benzene distilled off, the solid filtered, washed with ice-cold water, dried and recrystallised from methanol.

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Four such compounds were prepared (Table 2).

TABLE-2

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C	Molecular formula
1.	H	H	244	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl.2HCl
2.	Br	H	268	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ ClBr.2HCl
3.	Br	Br	270(d)	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂ ClBr ₂ .2HCl
4.	NO ₂	H	265(d)	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₄ Cl.2HCl

Yield ranged between 65-70%.
% N within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the theoretical values.
Isolated as hydrochlorides.

Substituted 3-[N-(1'-acetyl)-aminomethyl]quinazolono-2'-[phthalamido-alkyl] benzimidazoles: An equimolar mixture of (a) and (b) was refluxed in dry acetone (12 ml) in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.015 mole) for 3-4 hr. Excess acetone was distilled off and methanol added to the solid residue. The mixture was heated till the reactants dissolved leaving the potassium carbonate behind. Excess methanol was distilled off, the solution cooled and the solid after filtration and drying was recrystallised from methanol. Fourteen such compounds were synthesised (Table 3).

Scheme

Pharmacology :

For the evaluation of amoebicidal activity of the compounds, the method of Das *et al*¹³ was followed, except for the TPS-1 medium which was kept at pH 6.8 and not 7.2, since acidic pH is favourable for growth of the amoebae.

A three day old culture of *E. histolytica* was used and the final results were obtained after observing under an inverted microscope after 72 hr. Amoebicidal activity was carried out at 125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Out of the fourteen compounds screened, three were

TABLE-3

Sl. No.	R	R'	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Amoebicidal activity at 125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
1.	OH ₂	H	H	H	> 275	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄ .2HCl	NA
2.	OH ₂	H	Br	H	220(d)	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₆ O ₄ Br.2HCl	NA
3.	OH ₂	H	Br	Br	> 275	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₄ Br ₂ .2HCl	NA
4*	OH ₂	H	NO ₂	H	270(d)	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₆ O ₆ .2HCl	125
5.	OH ₂	H	H	H	> 275	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄ .2HCl	NA
6.	OH ₂ , OH ₂	H	Br	H	200(d)	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ N ₆ O ₄ Br.2HCl	NA
7.	OH ₂ , OH ₂	H	Br	Br	180(d)	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄ Br ₂ .2HCl	NA
8.	CH ₂ , OH ₂	H	NO ₂	H	> 275	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ N ₇ O ₆ .2HCl	NA
9.	CH ₂ , OH ₂	H	NO ₂	H	> 275	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₆ .2HCl	NA
10.	CH ₂	3-NO ₂	H	H	235(d)	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₇ O ₆ Br.2HCl	NA
11.	CH ₂	3-NO ₂	Br	Br	273(d)	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₆ Br ₂ .2HCl	NA
12*	CH ₂	3-NO ₂	Br	H	270(d)	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₇ O ₆ .2HCl	125
13*	CH ₂	3-NO ₂	NO ₂	H	273(d)	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ N ₇ O ₈ .2HCl	125
14.	CH ₂ , OH ₂	3-NO ₂	H	Br	> 275	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₆ Br ₂ .2HCl	NA

Yield ranged between 45-50%.
C, H, N ranged within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the theoretical values.
The compounds were isolated as hydrochlorides.
*Amoebicidal at 125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.
NA = Non-amoebicidal.

active at this concentration. Emetine hydrochloride and metronidazole (FLAGYL) were used as the standard drugs, the former was active as 62.5 µg/ml and the latter at 7.8 µg/ml at pH 6.8.

Results and Discussion

The results of the bioassay show that three compounds are active at 125 µg/ml. All the three compounds, i.e. no. 4, no. 12 and no. 13 (Table 3) have a nitro group either in the quinazolone moiety or in the phthalamido ring. The presence of a bromo group in the quinazolone ring system has not been effective in exhibiting the amoebicidal activity in these compounds. Therefore, the only conclusion that can be drawn from these results is that the nitro group, irrespective of its position is responsible for activity in the compounds.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. Nitya Nand, Director, C. D. R. I., for facilities for elemental and spectral screening and Dr. S. K. Gupta, Head, Microbiology Division, Dr. B. N. K. Prasad and Miss Indu Bansal for the bioassay of the compounds. One

of the authors (P. S.) is thankful to C. S. I. R., New Delhi, for a Junior Research Fellowship.

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